

Name/ First name	File number	Age

1- Medical History :

- Diabetes : yes / no
- HTA (Hypertension) : yes / no
- Dyslipidemia : yes / no
- Obesity : yes / no

2- Pelvic Surgery History : Yes / No

3- Pregnancy / Parity : G : P :

4- Hormonal Contraception : Yes / No

5- Ovarian Stimulation : Yes / No

6- Menopause : Yes / No

7- Symptomatic : Yes / No

8- Symptomatology / Circumstances of Discovery :

- Abdominal pain : yes / no
- Dysmenorrhea : yes / no
- Menometrorrhagia : yes / no
- Dyspareunia : yes / no
- Bowel habit changes : yes / no
- Urinary tract symptoms : yes / no
- General deterioration : yes / no
- Asymptomatic : yes / no

9- Physical Examination :

- **Palpable mass on abdominal examination : yes / no**
- **Palpable adnexal mass on pelvic exam : yes / no**
- **Speculum examination :**
 - Mass effect on the vagina : yes / no
 - Bleeding

10- Biological Data :

11- Pelvic Ultrasound :

- **Pelvic Ultrasound** : Performed / Not performed
- **Result** :

12- MRI Data :

- **Date** :
- **Number** :
- **Mass** : Unilateral – Bilateral
- **Mass Morphology** :
 - Cystic mass
 - Solid-cystic mass
 - Solid mass (>80% of the mass is solid)
- **Non-tissue solid portion** : Yes / No
 - Smooth and thin septa : - Fibrin septa : - Debris / Blood clots : - Hair / Ossifications : - Rokitansky protuberance :
- **Characteristics of the Fluid Content (Non-tissue)** :
 - Serous / Clear
 - Hemorrhagic
 - Endometriotic
 - Fatty
 - Proteinaceous
- **Tissue Portion** : Yes / No
- **Nature of the tissue portion** :
 - Irregular thick septa
 - Vegetations
 - Mural nodule / Papillary projection
- **Contours of the tissue portion** : Regular / Irregular
- **Contours of the non-tissue solid portion** : Regular / Irregular
- **Enhancement of the tissue portion** : Curve type 1 – Curve type 2 – Curve type 3
- **Mass Signal** :
 - T1 signal : Hypointense / Isointense / Hyperintense.
 - T2 signal : Hypointense / Isointense / Hyperintense.
 - Diffusion signal : Hypointense / Hyperintense
- **Tissue portion signal** :
 - T1 signal : Hypointense / Isointense / Hyperintense.
 - T2 signal : Hypointense / Isointense / Hyperintense.
 - Diffusion signal : Hypointense / Hyperintense

- **Measurements :**
 - Largest diameter of the entire mass : - Largest diameter of the solid tissue portion.
- **Complications:**
 - **Signs of Torsion :** Absent / Twisted pedicle / Ovarian edema / Ovarian infarction.
 - **Signs of infection :**
 - **Signs of Rupture :**
- **Other signs :**
 - **Peritoneal fluid :** Yes / No
 - **Peritoneal inclusion cyst :** Yes / No
 - **Peritoneal thickening :** Absent / Regular / Irregular
 - **Others :**
- **Pelvic adenopathies :** Yes / No
- **Signs of invasion of pelvic structures (Rectum – Bladder – Broad ligament – Parametria – Uterus) :** Yes / No
- **ORADS Classification :**
- **Measurement of the Apparent Diffusion Coefficient in the solid tissue portion.**

13- Histopathological Data :

- **Tumor Malignancy :** Benign – Malignant / Borderline.
- **Histological Type :**
- **Number of lymph nodes removed :**
- **Peritoneal metastasis :** Yes / No